

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

4th TNA Call Documentation – User Report (User)

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

After the StoRIES Transnational Access stay or Virtual Access, users are required to submit a *User Report*. This should be done within 4 weeks after the Access is completed unless otherwise agreed. The *User Report* will be given to the User(s) by the Project Management. The report contains sections related to the work performed, the main results and observations that were achieved.

This document should be completed, signed, and sent to the following person, along with the *TNA Cost Claim Form* and all eligible receipts either by e-mail to info@storiesproject.eu and olga.suminska-ebersoldt@kit.edu or by postal mail to:

*Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
Olga Sumińska-Ebersoldt
Geb 421
Hermann-von-Helmholtz-Platz 1
76344 Eggenstein-Leopoldshafen
Germany*

Summary questionnaire for users who have been granted Transnational Access (TNA) under the StoRIES project Horizon 2020 TNA scheme. More information on StoRIES TNA can be found in “[General Rules](#)” and in “[Access Policy](#)” which can be found on the StoRIES webpage.

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Hybrid Hydrogen Electrolyzer Systems for Grid Services
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	HHES-GS
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	P2X (LUT University)
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Alkaline electrolyzer, PEM electrolyzer, Hybrid systems, and Grid Services
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	1 st visit: 2024-06-15 2 nd visit: 2024-10-27
Departure date (from town where RI located)	1 st visit: 2024-06-21 2 nd visit: 2024-12-20
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	1 st visit: 2024-06-17 2 nd visit: 2024-10-28
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	1 st visit: 2024-06-20 2 nd visit: 2024-12-20
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	17 days

Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	14 of these days were weekends 1 day was national holiday in Finland (6 th of December) 2 days were taken as vacation
Number of days using the RI	41 days
Number of users granted access (group size)	One person
Comments	The research stay was divided in 2 visits. This was already specified in the application.
User	
User group leader or sole applicant (user group member 1)	
First name	[REDACTED]
Last name	[REDACTED]
Affiliation / Employer	KTH Royal Institute of Technology
Country of Employer	Sweden
E-mail	[REDACTED]
Comments	
User group member 2	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	
Country of Employer	
E-mail	
Comments	
User group member 3	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	
Country of Employer	
E-mail	
Comments	
User group member 4	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	

Country of Employer	
E-mail	
Comments	
Please insert more fields if your groups had more than four members.	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p><i>[Please describe short the main objectives of your project]</i></p> <p><i>The objectives of the proposed project were:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. Analysis of dynamics limitations of Alkaline and Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) electrolyzers from single cells and stacks, to large-scale electrolyzer systems.</i> <i>2. Maximization of Alkaline and PEM electrolyzer capabilities by their combination in Hybrid Hydrogen Electrolyzer Systems (HHESs).</i> <p><i>However, the Research Infrastructure (RI) was going through an upgrade of the facilities. Due to the delay in the construction works of the RI, the PEM electrolyzer was not available during the time of the visit. Therefore, the objectives of the project were redefined as follows:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>1. Performance analysis of alkaline electrolyzers for different power converter topologies from large-scale systems to single cell electrolyzers.</i> <i>2. Study of power quality, in both electrolyzer and grid side, and flexibility of the system for different power converter topologies, as well as combination of electrolyzers in hybrid systems with batteries or supercapacitors.</i> 	
Activities performed (up to 600 words)	
<p><i>[Please summarise the work carried you (steps taken, instrumentation used, techniques employed, data sources consulted etc.)]</i></p> <p>The research stay was divided in two visits. The 1st 1-week visit allowed the user to conducted some preliminary test and understand the capabilities of the RI. In the 2nd 8-week visit, the RI was used to obtain the desired experimental results. The activities performed through out the collaboration are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1st 1-week visit: Introduction to the RI. The visit allowed fully understanding the capabilities and limitations of the TNA infrastructure, get familiarize with the equipment with some preliminary tests, and enhance the cooperation with the members of the RI. • Between 1st and 2nd visit: Development of simulation models based on large-scale electrolyzer systems with different power converter topologies and hybrid configurations including batteries and supercapacitors. Furthermore, the objectives of the project are redefined considering the capabilities and limitation of the RI. • 2nd 8-week visit: Due to more extensive work during this visit. The activities are further divided below: 	

- Characterization of a single cell of Alkaline electrolyzer with using a potentiostat and a flexible power supply. Steady state tests and Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy were used to obtain the polarization curve and dynamic models for each of the single cell.
- Adaptation of the large-scale system simulations to the small-scale experimental system. The dynamic model of the single cell is simulated with different power converter topologies. From these simulations, realistic current waveforms for the different topologies are obtained to test in the experimental set up. Depending of the power converter topology, the power quality in the electrolyzer side can be better or worse.
- Experimental test of the current waveforms for different power converter topologies using the flexible power supply connected to the single cell alkaline electrolyzer. The current and voltage on the electrolyzer are measured and stored.
- Performance analysis of the experimental results. The power consumption of the electrolyzer is calculated for different power converter current waveforms at different set points. A relationship between power quality and increase of losses is observed.
- Comparison of experimental and simulation results, obtaining the same results in both cases. This confirms the accuracy of the obtained dynamic model of the single cell alkaline electrolyzer.
- After 2nd visit (ongoing work): Improvement of the large-scale system simulations with the dynamic model obtained from the small-scale experimental system, as well as study of the power quality in the grid side for the different power converter topologies, and the use of hybrid configurations to improve the flexibility of the system.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

[Summarise the (initial) outcomes of your study at the RI(s).]

The main scientific results achieved are as follows:

- Dynamic model of the single cell alkaline electrolyzer:
 - The EIS shows that the electrolyzers reacts in the same way for different perturbation amplitudes at higher frequency than 100 Hz. This is relevant as the ripple due to different power converter topologies have always a ripple higher than 300 Hz (case of the most simple power converter topology, 6-pulse thyristor rectifier).
 - The systems react different for different operation points (e.g. 20% or 100% of the nominal load). Therefore, the parameter of the dynamic model have to be updated depending of the operational point.
 - The comparison of the experimental and simulation results confirm the accuracy of the obtained model.
- Current waveforms for different power converter topologies:
 - Different power topologies have been simulated together with the dynamic electrolyzer model to obtain the current waveforms of the electrolyzers.
 - The current waveforms have been compared to the ones of industrial cases in literature to improve the simulation models and achieve a realistic representation of these waveforms.
- Performance analysis for different power converter topologies:

- The measurement from the experimental test show a relationship between the increase of losses and power quality of the current waveform. An increase of ripple amplitude in the current waveform increase the losses in the electrolyzer.
- Power converter topologies with the lowest power quality have an increase of losses in the electrolyzer. This is especially relevant in partial load operation, where the ripple amplitudes are higher.
- The simulation and measurement results obtain the same results. This validates the dynamic model of the electrolyzer, allowing further analysis in simulation, currently on going.
- Power quality of the grid side for different power converter topologies and hybrid configurations (on going work)
 - Analysis in simulations of the reactive power consumption and total harmonic distortion for different power converter topologies.
 - Hybrid configurations can enhance the performance of the system with batteries and/or supercapacitors acting a buffer of the possible fluctuations of active power due to the use of renewable energies.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

[Discuss the data obtained and describe the major scientific conclusions drawn.]

The experimental results obtained show that the power converter topology has an effect on the performance of the electrolyzer. A higher current ripple on the electrolyzer causes a higher increase of the losses. This makes highly relevant the correct selection of the power converter topology to minimize these losses. Thyristor rectifiers, especially 6-pulse thyristor rectifier, are the most used power converter topologies for large-scale electrolyzer system. However, these converter have higher ripples than transistor-based converters, increasing the losses in the electrolyzers.

The simulation results indicate that transistor-based can also increase the power quality in the grid side of the system, reducing the total harmonic distortion and reactive power consumption. When the increase of power quality in both grid and electrolyzer side is required, the use of transistor-converter are an attractive alternative to thyristor rectifiers.

Hybrid configurations of electrolyzers with supercapacitors or batteries are especially relevant when the system needs to be flexible to fluctuations of active power in the grid. This is the case of power system with a high share of renewable energies such as wind and solar. The fluctuations of the production of active power of the renewable source can be absorbed by the energy storage system so avoid changes in the operational set point of the electrolyzer.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

[Describe the main achievements during your stay at the site(s)]

The main achievements during the visits at the RI have been related with objective 1 of the project regarding the following results:

- Dynamic model of the single cell alkaline electrolyzer
- Current waveforms for different power converter topologies
- Performance analysis for different power converter topologies

The experimental work conducted in the RI allowed the accurate modelling of the single cell alkaline, as well as the validation of the simulations with experimental results. The validation of the simulation results also helped in the accurate modelling of the electrolyzer for objective 2 of the project.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

[List problems and issues you had, completing out your research project: Did you get access to all the necessary equipment, facilities, databases, etc.? If not, please specify the problems that occurred and list equipment the was not working or accessible.]

The project objectives had to be reformulated due to the ongoing construction works to upgrade the RI, making unavailable the use of a PEM electrolyzer. However, there was an excellent communication with the RI provider, and after the 1st 1-week visit, the objective of the project were reformulated to adapt it to the existing capabilities of the RI.

After the redefinition of the projects objectives, all the proposed activities have been successfully conducted in close collaboration between the user and the RI provider.

Intended publications

[Explain where and how you expect to publish the outcomes of your project work. Include also anything already published (What and where?)]

The results explained in the previous sections will be submitted for a journal publication to IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics.

Data management

[Describe the further usage and storage of project data]

The experimental results conducted by the user in the RI are stored by the user, and they will be use for the intended journal publication.

Conclusions / additional comments

[Provide any other comments you might have on your work]

The project had to be adapted to the capabilities and limitations of the RI due to ongoing constructions works to upgrade the RI. However, the communication and collaboration between the user and the RI providers was always very fruitful, and the project objectives where successfully adapted to these circumstances.

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction					
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments					
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>The objectives of the project had to be updated due to construction works at the Research Infrastructure, but the support in the process was excellent and the new objectives were successfully completed.</i>					
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify any problems]</i>					
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>The RI is in the process of been upgraded. The description of the equipment available in the facilities should be updated in the StoRIES website.</i>					
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify]</i>					
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				

<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>KOH electrolyte in the system</i>											
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>							
<i>[Comment]</i>											
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research											

[Please provide suggestions for specific type of facilities missing (RI gaps) or measurement / experiments you would like to perform which cannot be done on current StoRIES facilities]

Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.

I think the program is very useful, and it should could be further advertised so it reached more researchers

Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support

Awareness

Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES.

Yes No

*[Please specify how you learned about the pro-active innovation support]
Through StoRIES website*

Personal experience

Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support?

Yes No

*[Please provide details]
I ask them for advice during the application process and it was very helpful. They also put me in contact with the RI provider to improve my application*

Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Please provide details]

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

I have read the [StoRIES privacy policy](#) for participation in the StoRIES TNA and consent to participation and the associated data processing.

Date of submission to StoRIES TNA team: 2025-01-27

Your full name:

Your signature:

